

Preliminary Study

(Visualizing and Understanding the Internals of Fuzzing)

1 Background

This document contains the list of publications considered in the preliminary study on greybox fuzzing with the aim to map the claims/improvements and evaluation metrics to the categories shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Internal stages of greybox fuzzing that influence the fuzzing performance.

Each publication is carefully read to capture the necessary information and categorize the claims and metrics in the publication to the corresponding internal stage in the fuzzing. Section 2 provides the results of our study and the Section 3 provides details of the reviewed publications.

2 Results

Figure 2 shows the relationship between the number of claims (C) and evaluation metrics (M) with respect to the internal stages. All the claims and the evaluation metrics are categorised according to the internal stages of fuzzing (shown in the Figure 1)

Figure 2: Relationship between the number of claims (C) and the frequency with which a given evaluation metric (M) was used with respect to internal fuzzing stages.

3 Reviewed publications

This section provides details about the reviewed publications. Each publication is tagged with the internal stages and the content responsible for the categorization is also mentioned. For each publication, we record the following items,

- **Claims.** The claims or improvements mentioned in the publication.
- **Source (claims).** The text/information mentioned in the paper or the sections in the paper from where the claims are extracted.
- **Categorization (claims).** The categories for which the claims belong to in the Figure 1.
- **Comments (claims).** Some notes or observations that are relevant to the categorization of claims, if any were made.
- **Evaluation metrics.** The evaluation metrics mentioned in the publication.
- **Source (metrics).** The text/information mentioned in the paper or the sections in the paper from where the evaluation metrics are extracted.
- **Categorization (metrics).** The categories for which the evaluation metrics belong to in the Figure 1.
- **Comments (metrics).** Some notes or observations that are relevant to the categorization of the evaluation metrics, if any were made.

3.1 RLTG: Multi-targets directed greybox fuzzing [4]

- **Claims.** New seed scheduling algorithm (search strategy) and dynamic seed distance calculation (power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We propose adynamic seed distance calculation scheme that can address the indirect call and multi-targets directed fuzzing problems.
 - We propose anew seed scheduling algorithm based on the UCB algorithm. This algorithm can address the exploration and exploitation problem faced by existing seed scheduling strategy.

- **Categorization (claims).** *Search strategy, Power schedule*
- **Comments (claims).** Seed scheduling algorithm belongs to the search strategy and seed distance is used in energy computation in directed greybox fuzzing, hence, it belongs to power scheduling.
- **Evaluation metrics.** Vulnerability reproduction capability (Execution), number of testcases reaching different vulnerability sites (Execution), execution speed (Execution), testcase execution per second (Execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - we recorded the number of testcases that reached the target basic block.
 - we compared the crash reproduction capability.
 - we tested the execution speed.
 - we also compared the testcase execution per second.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** Vulnerability reproduction and number of testcases reaching different vulnerability sites are measured during execution of the target and does not directly evaluate the claims in search strategy and power schedule. The other metrics, execution speed and test case execution per second directly relate to the size of the testcases and can vary based on the hardware configuration. Hence, they are also categorised into Execution stage.

3.2 DiPri: Distance-Based Seed Prioritization for Greybox Fuzzing [12]

- **Claims.** Distance-based seed prioritization approach to boost greybox fuzzing which includes seed prioritization based on distances and seed selection algorithm (search strategy). DiPri can incur non-negligible time costs during fuzzing (execution), especially when calculating seed distances.
- **Source (claims.)**
 - we propose a distance-based seed prioritization approach, named DiPri, to facilitate greybox fuzzing.
 - novel yet general distance-based seed prioritization approach to boost greybox fuzzing.
 - DiPri can incur non-negligible time costs during fuzzing, especially when calculating seed distances.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Search strategy, Execution*
- **Comments (claims).** As seed prioritization mainly focuses on selecting the next best seed from the queue, it is categorised into search strategy.
- **Evaluation metrics.** Code coverage (execution), executions per run (execution), time overhead (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - The first metric is code coverage.
 - The second metric is executions per run.
 - Through our experiments, we find that DiPri can incur non-negligible time costs during fuzzing, especially when calculating seed distances.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*

- **Comments (metrics).** The metrics, code coverage and EPR correspond to how good are the improvements in terms of reaching more code. These metrics does not directly evaluate the claims directly. The computation overhead (measured in terms of time consumed by the algorithm) is categorised to *Execution*

3.3 DAFL: Directed Grey-box Fuzzing Guided by Data Dependency [6]

- **Claims.** Selective coverage instrumentation (instrumentation), semantic relevance scoring (search strategy, power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We present selective coverage instrumentation, a novel way to measure code coverage for DGF.
 - We devise semantic relevance scoring, a novel technique to effectively schedule seeds for DGF.
 - DAFL employs a novel scheduling algorithm that we call semantic relevance scoring.
 - The first use of our semantic relevance score is to prioritize the seeds for fuzzing.
 - The semantic relevance score also determines how much time to spend fuzzing each seed.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation, Search strategy, Power schedule*
- **Comments (claims).** The claim on selective instrumentation belongs to Instrumentation and semantic relevance scoring belongs to search strategy and power schedule.
- **Evaluation metrics.** Time to exposure (execution), reduction in number of instrumented functions (instrumentation).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - To evaluate the fuzzers, we measured the Time To Exposure (TTE) for each bug.
 - can reduce the number of instrumented functions.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution, Instrumentation*
- **Comments (metrics).** All the claims are evaluated only with respect to time to exposure which belongs to Execution stage. The selective instrumentation claim is also evaluated with respect to the number of reduced functions for instrumentation which belongs to Instrumentation (here the claim and evaluation is done in the same stage).

3.4 PosFuzz: augmenting greybox fuzzing with effective position distribution [20]

- **Claims.** An augmented greybox fuzzer with a mutation strategy sensitive to the mutation position (mutations).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - an augmented greybox fuzzer with a mutation strategy sensitive to the mutation position.
 - introduce a concept of effective position distribution to represent the semantics of the input, instead of the data type of the positions in the input. The distribution can be used to select the mutation positions with different weights, which can increase the ability to generate interesting input cases.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**

- **Evaluation metrics.** Edge coverage (execution), unique execution paths (execution), total number of unique bugs (execution), interesting test cases per input byte over time for havoc mutation strategy (mutations).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - We report edge coverage and unique executing paths.
 - The distribution of the interesting cases for both Pos-AFLFast and AFLFast with the x-axis being positions (1-byte slot) and the y-axis being the absolute number of interesting cases.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Mutations, Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** The first three metrics belong to execution strategy and are not related to mutation claim. However, the last metric directly evaluates the proposed claim and approach of mutation position improvement generates more interesting input cases.

3.5 Learning Seed-Adaptive Mutation Strategies for Greybox Fuzzing [7]

- **Claims.** Selecting mutation methods effectively using probability distribution (mutations).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - seed-adaptive approaches for selecting effective mutation methods.
 - to develop a new technique which automatically applies the proper probability distribution of choosing mutation methods to different seed inputs.
 - our technique for automatically learning optimized probability distributions of choosing effective mutation methods regarding to each seed input.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Branch coverage (execution), average number of crash inputs generated (execution), unique bugs found (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - effectively can our technique improve the performance of fuzzing technique in terms of branch coverage and crash input generation.
 - Can our approach find unique bugs that the existing techniques fail to detect.
 - SEAMFUZZ outperforms two baselines in terms of the number of covered branches and and found crash inputs.
 - without our seed clustering algorithm, the performance of the seed-adaptive approach in both path-finding and bug-detection ability significantly decreases.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** The improvements of mutation are evaluated based on coverage, crash inputs generated and unique bugs found which belong into execution stage.

3.6 Regression greybox fuzzing [18]

- **Claims.** Regression greybox fuzzing’s power schedule assigns more energy to seeds that execute code that has changed more recently or more frequently (power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**

- We also extend the concept of power schedules to the bytes of a seed and introduce Ant Colony Optimization to assign more energy to those bytes which promise to generate more interesting inputs.
- Specifically, a RGF’s power schedule assigns more energy to seeds that execute code that has changed more recently or more frequently.

- **Categorization (claims).** *Power Schedule*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Time to error (execution), number of crashing trails (execution), number of unique crashes (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - how the mean time-to-error, the number of crashing trials, and the average number of unique crashes.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.7 CSI-Fuzz: Full-speed edge tracing using coverage sensitive instrumentation [19]

- **Claims.** statically instruments directly at predetermined edges to only trace coverage-increasing test cases (instrumentation).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We accordingly design CSI-Fuzz utilizing coverage-sensitive instrumentation.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Edge discovery (execution), execution speed (instrumentation), bug discovery (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - The results of experiments demonstrate that CSI-Fuzz is effective and efficient in terms of edge discovery, execution speed, and bug discovery.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Instrumentation, Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** Improvements in instrumentation can be measure using target execution speed or increase in the program size. So, execution speed directly measures the claim in the Instrumentation. The other two metrics belong into the Execution stage.

3.8 Ankou: Guiding Grey-box Fuzzing towards Combinatorial Difference [10]

- **Claims.** presents an informative fitness function for grey-box fuzzing that we call distance-based fitness functions (power schedule, search strategy).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We present an informative fitness function for grey-box fuzzing that we call distance-based fitness functions.

- Note our fitness function only leverages readily available information in most state-of-the-art fuzzers, namely branch coverage.
- we propose adaptive seed pool update, a novel technique that dynamically selects the threshold to adaptively control the sensitivity of our fuzzer.

- **Categorization (claims).** *Power Schedule, Search strategy*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Number of crashes (execution), number of bugs (execution), number of test cases (execution), time to exposure (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - we report the number of unique crashes.
 - the test case generation throughput, the number of test cases the fuzzer produced per second.
 - ratio between the number of crashes.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.9 EcoFuzz: Adaptive Energy-Saving Greybox Fuzzing as a Variant of the Adversarial Multi-Armed Bandit [17]

- **Claims.** We proposed a VAMAB model to model the CGF, as well as proposed the reward probability which is the probability of the seed to discover new paths, method to estimate the reward probability for selecting seeds in the exploitation state (search strategy), adaptive power schedule that assigns energy to each seed by utilizing the average-cost as the baseline, and then monotonously increases the energy (power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - This method is more accurate than AFL’s search strategy for selecting the next seed with a high reward probability.
 - We recommended an adaptive power schedule that assigns energy to each seed by utilizing the average-cost as the baseline, and then monotonously increases the energy.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Power schedule, Search strategy*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** number of paths (execution), number of test cases (execution), average cost (execution), utilization ratio of energy (power schedule, search strategy).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - We choose the total number of paths discovered by different techniques, the total number of test cases generated, and the average-cost as the measurements.
 - utilization ratio of energy, which is the ratio of the energy consumed for finding the newest path to the total energy allocated in each turn, to evaluate the scheduling algorithms of different techniques.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Power schedule, Search strategy, Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.10 Smart greybox fuzzing [11]

- **Claims.** make greybox fuzzing input format-aware, smart mutation operators (mutations), validity based power-schedule (power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We define innovative mutation operators that work on the virtual file structure rather than on the bit level which allows SGF to explore completely new input domains while maintaining file validity.
 - We introduce a novel validity-based power schedule that enables SGF to spend more time generating files that are more likely to pass the parsing stage of the program, which can expose vulnerabilities much deeper in the processing logic.
 - AFLSMART assigns more energy to inputs which are more syntactically valid.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutation, Power schedule*
- **Comments (claims).** the new mutation operators fall into Mutation stage and the validity based power schedule falls into the Power Schedule stage.
- **Evaluation metrics.** unique crashes (execution), number of paths (execution), number of bugs (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - we investigate whether AFLSMART exposes more unique crashes than AFL/AFLFast.
 - whether AFLSMART explores more paths than AFL/AFLFAST in the given time budget.
 - we investigate whether AFLSMART exposes more unique crashes than Peach in 24 hours, and in the absence of crashes whether AFLSMART explores more paths than Peach in the given time budget.
 - we investigate the number of bugs found by each technique individually and all together.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** The new mutation operators are not evaluated directly and also the validity based power schedule. All the metrics belong into Execution stage.

3.11 AFLTurbo: Speed up Path Discovery for Greybox Fuzzing [13]

- **Claims.** Interruptible mutation (mutations), locality based mutation (mutations), hotspot-aware mutation (mutations).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - Interruptible mutation, which uses a hang monitor to avoid unnecessary mutation overhead.
 - Locality-based mutation, which utilizes mutation information in previous rounds to guide fuzzing useful regions in future rounds.
 - Hotspot-aware fuzzing, which exploits a pre-evaluation process to identify metadata and only mutates these regions.
 - three new approaches interruptible mutation, locality-based mutation and hotspot-aware fuzzing to improve AFL's speed of path discovery.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Path discovery (execution), vulnerability detection (execution).

- **Source (metrics.)**
 - To evaluate its effectiveness in terms of both path discovery and vulnerability detection.
 - AFLTurbo is evaluated in terms of both path discovery and bug detection on eight programs.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.12 REDQUEEN: Fuzzing with Input-to-State Correspondence. [1]

- **Claims.** Automatically overcomes checksums/magicbytes by observing the arguments of the function calls and compare instructions via virtual machine introspection. The observed values are used to provide inputs specific mutations (mutations).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - The resulting mutation operator is more efficient than all other mutation operator used by AFL.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** number of bugs found (execution), code coverage (execution), execution speed (execution), number of mutated inputs produced per time that increases coverage (mutations).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - we demonstrate that our tool is able to find novel bugs in various well-tested.
 - the number of basic blocks in a binary.
 - test on the number of basic blocks found in 10 hours.
 - Number of inputs that trigger paths with new coverage per time spent using different techniques.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Mutation, Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** "number of mutated inputs produced per time that increases coverage" directly evaluates the mutations and others fall into the execution stage.

3.13 Sequence Coverage Directed Greybox Fuzzing [8]

- **Claims.** we present a novel lightweight directed fuzzing technique SCDF, which is guided by a set of userspecified statement sequences. We also propose a novel energy schedule algorithm which adjusts a seed's energy according to its ability of covering the given statement sequences (power schedule).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - we present a novel energy schedule algorithm, which adjusts on demand a seed's energy according to its ability of covering the given statement sequences calculated on demand.
 - We implement the technique in a tool LOLLY in order to achieve efficiency both at instrumentation time and at runtime.
 - Therefore, SCDF Instrumentor only instruments the basic blocks each of which contains at least a target statement.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation, Power schedule*

- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Time to exposure (execution), instrumentation time (Instrumentation).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - Time-to-Exposure (TTE) measures the length of the fuzzing campaign until the first test input is generated that exposes a given vulnerability.
 - We evaluate the effectiveness of LOLLY in crash reproduction and compare it with AFLGo and BugRedux.
 - evaluated LOLLY to three application scenarios, i.e. true positive verification, crash reproduction, and bugs exposure.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution, Instrumentation*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.14 Superior: Grammar-Aware Greybox Fuzzing [14]

- **Claims.** we introduce two grammar-aware mutation strategies (i.e., enhanced dictionary-based mutation and tree-based mutation). we introduce a grammar-aware trimming strategy that can effectively trim test inputs while keeping the input structure valid (mutations).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - we introduce two grammar-aware mutation strategies (i.e., enhanced dictionary-based mutation and tree-based mutation).
 - we introduce a grammar-aware trimming strategy that can effectively trim test inputs while keeping the input structure valid.
 - we have demonstrated that our grammar-aware trimming strategy can effectively trim test inputs while keeping them syntax-valid; and our grammar-aware mutation strategies can effectively generate new test inputs that can trigger new coverage.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** bug finding capability (execution), function coverage (execution), trimming ratio, grammar validity ratio, mutation strategy efficiency by measuring interesting inputs generated (mutations), performance overhead of parsing the inputs (milliseconds).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - Superior can improve the code coverage (i.e., 16.7% and 8.8% in line and function coverage) and bug-finding capability i.e., 34 new bugs.
 - how is the bug-finding capability of superior?
 - How is the code coverage of Superior?
 - compares the trimming ratio (i.e., the ratio of bytes trimmed from test inputs) and the grammar validity ratio (i.e., the ratio of test inputs that are grammar-valid after trimming).
 - shows the number of interesting test inputs (i.e., triggering new coverage) discovered by different mutation strategies as we fuzzed.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Mutation, execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.15 Hawkeye: Towards a Desired Directed Grey-box Fuzzer [2]

- **Claims.** We proposed a novel approach to boost the convergence speed to the target sites by utilizing power scheduling (power schedule), adaptive mutation (mutations) and seed prioritization (search strategy).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We proposed a novel approach to boost the convergence speed to the target sites by utilizing power scheduling, adaptive mutation and seed prioritization.
 - For AFLGo, as mentioned in §2.2.2, the shorter paths will be assigned more energy, which may starve longer paths that are still reachable to the target sites. To mitigate this, we propose the power function that considers both trace distance (based on basic block level distance) and trace similarities (based on covered function similarity).
 - Algo. 1 shows the workflow of our adaptive mutation, given a seed s . The basic idea is to give less chance of coarse-grained mutations when the seed s can reach the target functions.
 - Instead, we provide a three-tiered queue which appends newly generated seeds into different categories according to their scores.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Power schedule, Mutations, Search strategy*
- **Comments (claims).** There are improvements in all the three stages of fuzzing.
- **Evaluation metrics.** Time to exposure (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - We use “time-to-exposure” (TTE) to measure the length of the fuzzing campaign until the first test input is generated that triggers a given error.
 - In this experiment, we directly compare Hawkeye with other fuzzers on some known crashes to evaluate its crash exposure capability.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** None of the improvements are directly evaluated

3.16 CollAFL: Path Sensitive Fuzzing [3]

- **Claims.** an algorithm to resolve the hash collision issue in AFL, improving its edge coverage accuracy with a low-overhead instrumentation scheme (instrumentation), three new coverage sensitive seed selection policies increase fuzzer performance (search strategy).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - CollAFL could reduce the edge collision ratio to nearly zero.
 - It mitigates path collisions by providing more accurate coverage information, while still preserving low instrumentation overhead.
 - We proposed three new coverage sensitive seed selection policies. Our empirical results confirmed that prioritizing seeds based on accurate edge coverage information significantly improves fuzzers’ performance.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation, Search strategy*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** edge collision ratio, number of instructions instrumented (instrumentation), code coverage (execution), number of unique paths (execution), vulnerability discovery (execution), crashes over time (execution).

- **Source (metrics.)**
 - Moreover, armed with the three fuzzing strategies, CollAFL outperforms AFL in terms of both code coverage and vulnerability discovery.
 - the code coverage and crash growth improvements, the effectiveness of bug finding of our fuzzer in real world applications.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Instrumentation, execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** Number of instructions instrumented and edge collision ratio directly evaluates the improvements in Instrumentation.

3.17 BEACON: Directed Grey-Box Fuzzing with Provable Path Pruning [5]

- **Claims.** static analysis for computing necessary conditions for reaching the given testing target (used in instrumentation), a directed grey-box fuzzer that can prune a large number of infeasible paths, selective instrumentation (instrumentation).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - In BEACON, we instrument two kinds of statements: variable-defining statements and branch statements.
 - We instrument the program using the inferred necessary precondition to prune infeasible paths at runtime.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation*
- **Comments (claims).** The approach performs static analysis and instruments the target to prune infeasible paths at runtime. There is no change in the fuzzing algorithm. The approach only instruments the target.
- **Evaluation metrics.** Vulnerability reproduction time (execution), fuzzing time reaching targets (execution), instrumentation runtime overhead (instrumentation).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - First, we compared BEACON with four state-of-the-art (directed) fuzzers in the application scenario of vulnerability reproduction.
 - we also evaluated how much they contribute to the time reduction in fuzzing.
 - we also evaluated the runtime overhead introduced by our instrumentation, which aims to show the effectiveness of our instrumentation strategy.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Instrumentation, execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** One of the metrics directly evaluate the Instrumentation stage (through instrumentation runtime overhead) and the others fall into Execution stage.

3.18 DeepFuzzer: Accelerated Deep Greybox Fuzzing [9]

- **Claims.** fuzzer with qualified seed generation (initial seeds), balanced seed selection (search strategy, power schedule), and hybrid seed mutation (mutation).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - we present DeepFuzzer, an enhanced greybox fuzzer with qualified seed generation, balanced seed selection, and hybrid seed mutation.
 - DeepFuzzer employs symbolic execution to generate initial seeds.

- DeepFuzzer utilizes the balanced seed selection to give adequate mutation times for each seed.
- we propose a hybrid mutation strategy which combines the restricted-mutation strategy and the random mutation strategy.
- The balanced seed selection aims at assigning balanced mutation times to each seed. We propose two rules named the branch-sensitive fair skip rule and the branch-sensitive energy assignment rule to make the fuzzing tend to be in equilibrium.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Initial seeds, Search strategy, Power schedule, Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).** The approach contains the information about having improvements in all the four categories of the fuzzing.
- **Evaluation metrics.** number of paths (execution), number of branches (execution), number of crashes (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - The number of paths executed, branches covered, and unique crashes triggered are used as metrics.
 - We use three metrics to evaluate the results of fuzzers on these ten real-life projects. These metrics consist of the number of exercised paths, covered branches, and triggered unique crashes.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).** All the metrics directly fall into Execution stage

3.19 LearnAFL: Greybox Fuzzing With Knowledge Enhancement [16]

- **Claims.** LearnAFL uses these format information to mutate the seeds (mutations), which is efficient to explore deeper paths and reduce the test cases.
- **Source (claims.)**
 - Then LearnAFL uses these format information to mutate the seeds, which is efficient to explore deeper paths and reduce the test cases exercising high-frequency paths than AFL.
 - assistant mutation algorithm. This algorithm is mainly used to mutate the seeds with the format knowledge.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Mutations*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Branch coverage (execution), unique crashes (execution), vulnerability discovery (execution).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - We choose the basic block transitions coverage achieved by different techniques through time as the primary metric.
 - we evaluate the ability to explore deep paths and discovery vulnerabilities.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution*
- **Comments (metrics).**

3.20 Fine-Grained Coverage-Based Fuzzing [15]

- **Claims.** Mutates the SUT with additional branches to preserve already generated seeds (instrumentation).
- **Source (claims.)**
 - We achieve this by making the test objectives defined by these metrics (such as conditions to activate or mutants to kill) explicit as new branches in the target program. Fuzzing such a modified target is then equivalent to fuzzing the original target.
 - by relying on a dedicated transformation of the code of the PUT.
 - This mechanism involves instrumenting the fuzzed code with additional branches.
- **Categorization (claims).** *Instrumentation*
- **Comments (claims).**
- **Evaluation metrics.** Throughput (execution), size of seeds pool, edge coverage (execution), number of bugs (execution), build slowdown (instrumentation).
- **Source (metrics.)**
 - how are the fuzzers (1) throughput, (2) size of seeds pool, (3) achieved edge coverage and (4) number of detected bugs in the PUT.
 - Code instrumentation slows down the program builds, as instrumentation itself takes time to complete and the instrumented program is larger to compile.
- **Categorization (metrics).** *Execution, Instrumentation*
- **Comments (metrics).**

References

- [1] C. Aschermann, S. Schumilo, T. Blazytko, R. Gawlik, and T. Holz, “Redqueen: Fuzzing with input-to-state correspondence.” in *NDSS*, vol. 19, 2019, pp. 1–15.
- [2] H. Chen, Y. Xue, Y. Li, B. Chen, X. Xie, X. Wu, and Y. Liu, “Hawkeye: Towards a desired directed grey-box fuzzer,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM SIGSAC conference on computer and communications security*, 2018, pp. 2095–2108.
- [3] S. Gan, C. Zhang, X. Qin, X. Tu, K. Li, Z. Pei, and Z. Chen, “Collaff: Path sensitive fuzzing,” in *2018 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 679–696.
- [4] Y. He and Y. Zhu, “Rltg: Multi-targets directed greybox fuzzing,” *Plos one*, vol. 18, no. 4, p. e0278138, 2023.
- [5] H. Huang, Y. Guo, Q. Shi, P. Yao, R. Wu, and C. Zhang, “Beacon: Directed grey-box fuzzing with provable path pruning,” in *2022 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, 2022, pp. 36–50.
- [6] T. E. Kim, J. Choi, K. Heo, and S. K. Cha, “DAFL: Directed grey-box fuzzing guided by data dependency,” in *32nd USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 23)*. Anaheim, CA: USENIX Association, Aug. 2023, pp. 4931–4948. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity23/presentation/kim-tae-eun>
- [7] M. Lee, S. Cha, and H. Oh, “Learning seed-adaptive mutation strategies for greybox fuzzing,” in *2023 IEEE/ACM 45th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 384–396.

- [8] H. Liang, Y. Zhang, Y. Yu, Z. Xie, and L. Jiang, “Sequence coverage directed greybox fuzzing,” in *2019 IEEE/ACM 27th International Conference on Program Comprehension (ICPC)*, 2019, pp. 249–259.
- [9] J. Liang, Y. Jiang, M. Wang, X. Jiao, Y. Chen, H. Song, and K.-K. R. Choo, “Deepfuzzer: Accelerated deep greybox fuzzing,” *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 2675–2688, 2021.
- [10] V. J. Manès, S. Kim, and S. K. Cha, “Ankou: Guiding grey-box fuzzing towards combinatorial difference,” in *2020 IEEE/ACM 42nd International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2020, pp. 1024–1036.
- [11] V.-T. Pham, M. Böhme, A. E. Santosa, A. R. Căciulescu, and A. Roychoudhury, “Smart greybox fuzzing,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 47, no. 9, pp. 1980–1997, 2021.
- [12] R. Qian, Q. Zhang, C. Fang, and Z. Chen, “Dipri: Distance-based seed prioritization for greybox fuzzing (registered report),” in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Fuzzing Workshop*, ser. FUZZING 2023. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2023, pp. 21–30. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3605157.3605172>
- [13] L. Sun, X. Li, H. Qu, and X. Zhang, “Aflturbo: Speed up path discovery for greybox fuzzing,” in *2020 IEEE 31st International Symposium on Software Reliability Engineering (ISSRE)*, 2020, pp. 81–91.
- [14] J. Wang, B. Chen, L. Wei, and Y. Liu, “Superion: Grammar-aware greybox fuzzing,” in *2019 IEEE/ACM 41st International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, 2019, pp. 724–735.
- [15] W.-C. Wu, B. Nongpoh, M. Nour, M. Marcozzi, S. Bardin, and C. Hauser, “Fine-grained coverage-based fuzzing,” *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.*, mar 2023, just Accepted. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3587158>
- [16] T. Yue, Y. Tang, B. Yu, P. Wang, and E. Wang, “Learnaf1: Greybox fuzzing with knowledge enhancement,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 117 029–117 043, 2019.
- [17] T. Yue, P. Wang, Y. Tang, E. Wang, B. Yu, K. Lu, and X. Zhou, “EcoFuzz: Adaptive Energy-Saving greybox fuzzing as a variant of the adversarial Multi-Armed bandit,” in *29th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 20)*. USENIX Association, Aug. 2020, pp. 2307–2324. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/usenixsecurity20/presentation/yue>
- [18] X. Zhu and M. Böhme, “Regression greybox fuzzing,” in *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, 2021, pp. 2169–2182.
- [19] X. Zhu, X. Feng, X. Meng, S. Wen, S. Camtepe, Y. Xiang, and K. Ren, “Csi-fuzz: Full-speed edge tracing using coverage sensitive instrumentation,” *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 912–923, 2020.
- [20] Y. Zou, W. Zou, J. Zhao, N. Zhong, Y. Zhang, J. Shi, and W. Huo, “PosFuzz: augmenting greybox fuzzing with effective position distribution,” *Cybersecurity*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 11, June 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://cybersecurity.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s42400-023-00143-2>